

Does Corporate Governance Attributes Influence on Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure and Financial Stability: Stakeholder theory Approach

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Abstract

The core objective of this research study is to examine the influence of corporate governance (CGA) on corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSRDI) and financial stability in conventional banks of Pakistan. The data collected for this research study from the annual reports of 18 listed banks on the stock market over 12 years, from the period of 2010 to 2021. Multiple regression was run to investigate the influence of the corporate governance on corporate social responsibility disclosure and financial stability. The data is collected for this study from the annual reports of the conventional banks from the period of the 2010 to 2021. Multiple regression was run to investigate the influence of the corporate governance on corporate social responsibility disclosure, financial stability and profitability. The research works finds that corporate governance plays a significant role on the corporate social responsibility disclosure. Furthermore, board size, independent director has positive and significantly enhance the financial stability and profitability models.

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Introduction

In recent decades, corporate social responsibility activities gain a great momentum in the field of the research globally (Benlemlih and Girerd-potin, (2017). The term corporate social responsibility is not a cost for the company it should deal an asset. The CSR is not just a social response to the society, but the CSR commitments toward the welfare of the society in case of donation, vision, mission, and environmental responsibility toward the society by the company which deals in a proper way (Shahin and Zairi, 2007). While, Gill, (2008) reveals that the main agenda of the CSR is not to maximize the shareholder wealth but its deals with the environmental and social issues of the society. Furthermore, the study reveals that the companies must disclose the information of the corporate social responsibility in financial statements of company to meet the stakeholder needs (Gelb and Steawser, 2001).

Additionally, the research says that management must disclose all types of the information in financial statements to reduce the information asymmetry between the management of the company and stakeholder of the company (Ho and Taylor, 2013). MacWilliam's and Siegel (2001) defined the CSR as a voluntary activity toward the society and environmental issue. Similarly, Whait et al. (2018) defined that, CSR is an activity of the business commitment to resolve the environmental and social issues of society. Shleifer and Vishny, (1997) reveals that CG attributes ensure in firm that stakeholder get return on their investment in firms. Berle and Means (1932) defined, that CG mechanism provided the formal structure to firm as well as resolve the agency conflicts among the stakeholder, management and principles of the firms. Corporate governance (CG) defined as the rules and regulations that firms are directed and controlled. In wider sense, CG is defined, the firm procedures, rule of law through company controlled, directed and enhance the shareholder wealth.

Salvi et al. (2020) says that CSR is an intangible resource for the company and intangible more valuable than tangible resource. Barney, (1991) reveals that according to the theory resource-based view, tangible and intangible resources are increasing the financial performance of company. Furthermore, research study examines that CSR has positive influence on the financial stability of Islamic banks and financial stability was measured through the Z-index (Kamal et al. 2021 and Kamal et al. 2022). Additionally, Kamal et al. (2021) investigates the influence of the corporate governance index on financial stability, for this purpose the research study collected data from the period of 2008 to 2020, they found that CG index significantly accelerates the financial stability of the banking sector in Pakistan.

Multiple regression analysis technique to check the influence of the CG on CSR index disclosures, for this purpose the study collected data from the period of 2011 to 2018 from the annual reports of Indonesia 10 Islamic banks, they found that CG mechanism has significantly enhanced the CSR (Ridwan and Mayapada,

2022). Moreover, the study also investigates the effect of CG mechanism on CSR disclosure, for this purpose the research works collected data from the annual reports of the companies from the period of the 2010 to 2021, matched observation method was used to investigate the influence of CG on CSR disclosure, the study found that CG has positive influence on the CSR disclosure (Lone et al. 2016).

Moreover, the research works is to investigate the influence of the CG on company CSR, for this purpose the research study collected the annual data of the for the period of 2007 to 2011, the research found that CG has positive and significant impact on the company CSR activities (Majeed et al. 2015). Khan et al. (2018) explores the relationship among the CG and quality of CSR of Pakistan listed stock exchange firms, for this purpose the study collected from the 2011 to 2017 the results signify that CH has positive and significantly improve the CSR practices. Data collected from the commercial banks of Kazakhstan stock exchange from the period the 2010 to 2016, to investigate the impact of the corporate governance on corporate social responsibility, they found that board gender diversity has positive while board size and independent directors has significant influence on the CSR activities (Orazalin, 2019). Using content analysis approach to investigate the influence of the corporate governance mechanism on the corporate social responsibility, they found that CG has positive and significant influence on CSR of the banks (Al Maeni et al. 2022).

Several, finance theories such agency theory, RBV theory and stewardship can be used for the association among the corporate governance and corporate social responsibility. Accordingly, Rodriguez-Fernandez, (2016) says that the stakeholder theory is unique theory to build up the relationship among the CG and corporate social responsibility. Hill and Jones (1992) say that stakeholder theory build up the association among the corporate stakeholder in the both cases explicitly and implicitly. Freeman (1983) reveals that stakeholder are group of the that whose claim against the company creditor, suppliers, customer and local community. Social engagement is one of the most important concepts that base on the stakeholder theory. The main aim of the CSR is to protect and resolve the local community social and environmental issue (Schwartz and Carroll, 2003).

Hypothesis development

H1: Board size has significant influence on the corporate social responsibility disclosure

H2: Independents boards has significant effects on the corporate social responsibility disclosure

H3: CEO duality has significant consequence on the corporate social responsibility disclosure

H4: Annual meeting has significant influence on the corporate social responsibility disclosure

H5: Board size has significant enhance on the financial stability & Profitability

H6: Independents boards has significant influence on the financial stability & Profitability

H7: CEO duality has significant enhance on the financial stability & Profitability

H8: Annual meeting has significant influence on the financial stability & Profitability

Theoretical Framework

Research method

Variable's measurement

The main independent variable corporate governance was measured the different proxies, shari'ah Supervisory board size if have the education we give 1 rank otherwise 0, independent directors, dual CEO and annual meeting of the board. Corporate social responsibility disclosure index (CSRDI) was measured by the prior literature (Palonova et al. 2018). This study bring minor change were introduced to make its suitable for the Pakistan environment. 20 items were selected to make the index of the corporate social responsibility, namely zakah, product and service, donation, health sectors, education, vision and mission statement, welfare, employee, charity see appendix. CSRDI was measured through where banks engaged in corporate social

role of CEO, duality of CEO only is strong positive and significant with the return on equity. Annual meeting is positive and significant correlation within all cases at 1% level. Banks age and Banks size is strong positive correlation with all 3 model. The correlation tables shows that there is no negative relationship among with the corporate governance and CSR on the banks. The tables also shows that corporate governance has no negative links with the financial stability and profitability. So, the research has positive and significant association among the variables only few variables which has highly correlated with the dependent variable.

Table 3. Correlation of Matrix

Variable's	FS	ROA	ROE	CSR	BS	ID	CEO	BM	BD	Age	Size
FS	1										
ROA	0.472***	1									
ROE	0.381***	0.614***	1								
CSR	0.482***	0.731***	0.234***	1							
BS	0.290***	0.471***	0.391***	0.231***	1						
ID	0.391***	0.401***	0.271***	0.182***	0.281***	1					
CEO	0.431***	0.581***	0.713***	0.571***	0.371***	0.581***	1				
BM	0.371***	0.512***	0.456**	0.361***	0.571**	0.451***	0.271***	1			
BD	0.345***	0.471***	0.191**	0.421***	0.290**	0.643***	0.319***	0.021***	1		
Age	0.691***	0.7821***	0.816**	0.712***	0.321*	0.182***	0.430***	0.191***	0.219***	1	
Size	0.732***	0.871***	0.690*	0.531***	0.591**	0.631***	0.458***	0.391***	0.518***	0.691***	1

Result interpretation & Discussion

Table 4 shows the results of the hypothesis testing in this study. Based on the hypothesis development this research has five hypotheses with **H.8**. This research study has following results. **H1-** board size has positively and significant at 1% and board size is significant at 5% and 1% level. **H2-** supported statistically at the probability significant at 1% and 5%. **H3-** Dual CEO supported statistically at the probability in the two model at 1% and 5%. **H4-** Annual boards meeting supported the hypothesis Model I at 1%, MII at 1% and MIII at 5% level of significance. **H5-** board size supported the hypothesis at 5% and 1% level of significant. **H6-** independents of directors has positive and significant influence on the financial stability and profitability and supported the hypothesis at 1% of level of significance. **H7-H8** supported the hypothesis at 1% accepted annual meeting of the board at only significant at 5%. This research works finds consistence with the prior research that corporate board size has positive and significant influence on the CSR in the Jordan context (Al Amosh, 2020). Moreover, the research also examine that the board size and independents of director has positive and significant influence on the CSR disclosure (Veronica Tibiletti et al. 2021). This research finding also contradict with the international studies.

Table. 4Regression Effect of CG on Corporate Social Responsibility Index, FinancialStability & Profitability

Variable's	CSR(M1)	VIF	FS(M2)	VIF	ROA(M2)	VIF	Sig (MI)	Sig (MII)	Sig (MIII)
Board Size	0.271	1.289	0.218	1.289	0.032	1.289	***	**	***
Independents Directors	0.312	1.451	0.119	1.451	0.291	1.451	***	**	**
CEO Duality	0.291	1.763	0.291	1.763	0.008	1.763	***	***	***
Boards Meeting	0.253	1.809	0.112	1.809	0.027	1.809	***	***	**
Banks Deposits	0.001	2.789	0.319	2.789	0.561	2.789	**	**	**
Banks Age	0.056	1.167	0.690	1.167	0.781	1.167	**	**	**
Banks Size	0.023	1.189	0.589	1.189	0.891	1.189	**	**	**
C	11.56***		-1.89***		-6.57**		***	***	**
Adj.R ²	0.231		0.367		0.281				
P-Value	0.000		0.000		0.000				
D-Watson	1.76		1.54		1.59				

* 10%, **5%, ***1%

Conclusion and Future direction

The main purpose of this research works is to explore the influence of the corporate governance attributes on the CSR disclosure and financial stability of conventional banks of Pakistan. The main findings of this research board size significantly enhance the CSR disclosure in the conventional banks. That means that board size efficiently uses the CSR practices in the conventional sectors. Board size play a key role on the CSR and financial stability of the banks in Pakistan. The research also find that independents of director also has

significantly enhance the CSR and financial stability of the banks. The role of dual chief executive has positively influence on the CSR and financial stability and profitability. The annual meeting of the boards plays a significant role on the CSR and financial stability of the banks. This research works contributed to the literature the corporate governance attribute plays a key role on the CSR and financial stability and profitability of the conventional and Pakistan. Furthermore, the research can be conducted the Islamic banks sector and also the comparison of the conventional and Islamic banks social responsibility. Additionally, the same research works study can be conducted in KSE 100 non-financial firms of Pakistan. Furthermore, the research can be conducted other attributes of the corporate governance with large sample of the banks. The research limited to only few corporate governance attributes as well as corporate social responsibility disclosure. The sample size of the banks is limited. The is no comparative study analysis in this research study.

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